

Co-Crystallisation of the ALK2/FKBP12 complex with compounds from M4K and others.

Rationale:

New compounds developed by M4K and other collaborators against ALK2 would benefit from solving their crystal structure to explain exactly how these compounds bind and help us work out how to improve them for both potency and selectivity. This requires protein crystals.

Aim:

Purify ALK2 (containing the kinase domain and the GS loop region - just above the Kinase domain) and it's binding partner FKBP12 which binds over the GS loop (previous attempts at co-crystallisation with ALK2 alone were not successful). Then set up crystal plates with 6 different compounds.

Protein Purification

Proteins to be purified:

ALK2 (wt longform containing Kinase domain and GS loop)

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MGHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQ/*SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHSTSGSGSGLPFLVQRTVARQITLLECVGKGRYG
EVWRGSWQGENVAVKIFSSRDEKSWFRETELYNTVMLRHENILGFASDMTSRHSSTQLWLITHYHEMGSLYDYL
QLTTLDTVSCLRIVLSIASGLAHLHIEIFGTQGKPAIAHRDLKSKNILVKKNGQCCIADLGLAVMHSQSTNQLDVGNN
PRVGTKRYMAPEVLDETIQVDCFDSYKRVDIWAFLVLEWEVARRMVSNGIVEDYKPPFYDVPNDPSFEDMRKV
VCVDQQRPNIPNRWFSPTLTLAKLMKECWYQNP SARLTALRIKKT LTKID
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FKBP12 (GST-tagged)

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MHHHHHHSSMSPILGYWKIKGLVQPTRLLEYLEEKYEEHLYERDEGDKWRNKKFELGLEFPNLPYYIDGDVKLTQS
MAIRYIADKHNMLGGCPKERAEISMLEGAVLDIRYGVSR IAYSKDFETLKVDFLSKLPEMLKMFEDRLCHKTYLNG
DHVTHPDFMLYDALDVVLYMDPMCLDAFPKLVCFKKRIEAIPIQIDKYLKSSKYIAWPLQGWQATFGGGDHPPKSS
SGVDLGTENLYFQ/*SMGVQVETISPGDGRTFPKRGQTCVVHYTGMLEDGKKFDSSRD RNKPFKFM LGKQEVIRG
WEEGVAQMSVGQRAKLTISPDYAYGATGHPGIIPPHATLVFDVELLKE
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/* denotes Tev cleavage site

Expression:

ALK2 was expressed in Sf9 insect cells by Katarzyna Kupinska at 27°C for 72 hours in glass shaker flasks.

FKBP12 was expressed in *E.coli* Rossetta cells by Ros Adamson, at 37C until OD600 1.1, induced with 0.4mM IPTG and subsequently grown overnight at 18C before harvesting.

Purification:

- Thaw pellets in luke warm water
- Sonicate FKBP1AA for 5 min (5 on, 10 off) on ice.
- Sonicate ACVR1A-c076 for 3 min (5 on, 10 off) on ice.

- Divide each pellet into two centrifugation tubes and top up with 'binding buffer' (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5) so each tube is full (approx 40ml per tube).
- Add 1ml PEI (5%) per tube to precipitate DNA.
- Spin at 21.5k rpm for 50 minutes.
- Incubate lysate with 2ml pre-equilibrated Ni-NTA beads at 4C for 1h. (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5)
- Spin down beads at 700g for 10 minutes to separate beads from lysate.
- Pour off lysate.
- Resuspend beads in 50ml binding buffer and load onto gravity flow column (collect flow through)
- Wash with 30ml wash buffer (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 30mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 7ml elution buffer 1 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 50mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 3 x 7ml elution buffer 4 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 250mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Add 1mM TCEP to all fractions.
- Run samples on an SDS PAGE gel (mix 5ul of loading dye with 15ul sample, boil for 3 minutes and load 10ul onto the gel.) and run at 160V for 50 minutes.
- Pool elution fractions E1 - E4(3)
- Add Tev protease to fractions which contain protein (Wash 2, E1, E4 (1-3))
- Incubate at 4C overnight.

Samples corresponding to the nickle column fractions run on an SDS PAGE – FT (flowthrough), W1(wash with binding buffer), W2 (wash with wash buffer), E1 (elution with E1 elution buffer), E4₍₁₋₃₎ (three elution's with elution 4 buffer)

- Concentrate down ACVR1A/ALK2 samples to <5ml and run on a pre-equilibrated GF 200 column (300mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Collect fractions and run a gel of peak.
- Concentrate down FKBP12 then dilute out imidazole to approx 5mM Imidazole. Incubate with pre-equilibrated Ni NTA beads (2ml bed volume) for 30 minutes.
- Load onto a gravity flow column and collect flow through.
- Wash with 30 ml wash buffer
- Elute with 15ml E4 buffer
- Run gel of fractions.

Regrettably it seems that a) FKBP12 didn't properly cleave and b) all forms are in all fractions bar the wash.

ACVR1/ALK2 SDS PAGE gel (top left) shows samples from the relevant size exclusion column fractions, corresponding to the UV peak shown in the bottom panel. The FKBP12 Nickel rebind SDS PAGE (top right) shows all samples in all fractions bar the wash: S (starting mix), FT (flowthrough), W (wash), E (elution).

- Pool fractions back together and add more tev and leave overnight.
- Then concentrate back down to <5ml and run on a GF75 column - this should separate out all species (GST alone will run as a dimer of around 60kDa, uncleaved will run as a dimer of around 80kDa - both of these are likely to come out very quickly or in the void of a 75).

Meanwhile, FKBP12 cleaved should run as 12kDa and come out towards the end of the run very separate from contaminants.

- Run gels of relevant fractions (5µl dye, 15µl sample, boil for 5 min and run 10µl at 170V for 50min.)

Separation of cleaved and uncleaved FKBP12. SDS PAGE (top) shows fractions corresponding to UV peaks from the SEC (bottom).

- Mix FKBP12 with ACVR1 with excess FKBP12.
- FKBP12 - 12ml of 36µM
- ACVR1A - 15ml of 22.6µM
- Mix at 1:1 ratio for FKBP12 excess. 12ml + 12ml.
- Concentrate down to <5ml and purify on GF75 to hopefully isolate the complex from free FKBP12
- Run a gel of the results.

Separation of complexed ALK2/FKBP12, free FKBP12 and higher mass aggregates. SDS PAGE (top) shows fractions corresponding to UV peaks from the SEC (bottom).

- Concentrate down fractions B5 – C3 for use in crystal plates.
- Mass spec complex

Mass spec confirms presence of the correct constructs in the complex.

Co-crystallisation setup:

Compounds:

M4K2009 - PK012002a

M4K1071 - PK008982b

M4K2044 - PK012055a

M4K2046 - PK012057a

E6201 - K63275 / PK010701a

Compounds were incubated with concentrated protein (12.5mg/ml) for 10 minutes. Samples were spun at 14,000 rpm for 10 minutes to remove precipitant.

Plates were set up of the protein complex with one of six ligands. Four plates were set up per ligand, using four in-house coarse screens (HCS3, HIN3, BSC6 and JCSG7).

Protein was used at 12.5mg/ml and compound was at 1mM with the exception of compound CP466722 used at 8.4mg/ml

Plates were set up using a mosquito machine at 150nl drops in 1:2, 1:1 and 2:1 ratios with the exception of E6201 which was accidentally set up at all 1:1 ratios. BSC6 and JCSG7 plates were left to incubate at 20°C while HCS3 and HIN3 plates were left to incubate at 4°C in each case.

Photographs of drops were regularly scheduled and will be reviewed using TexRank and scored accordingly.

Compound:

CP466722 – PK006099b

Due to low solubility of compound, a 5mM solution of CP466722 was made by Ros, added to a dilute sample of protein (aprox 0.4mg) before re-concentrating the protein back down to 8.5mg/ml.

Plates were then set up as above.

Review:

Plates were viewed at 4d post setup and scored for crystals: (**bold** wells are particularly of note)

Plate	Compound	Wells with mountable crystals
CI070149 (HIN3)	M4K2009	D8a
CI070144 (HCS3)	M4K1071	E6d
CI070141 (HIN3)	M4K2044	G3a F8a H4a F9a H10a F5a H2c F8c F5c H7a E9d
CI070140 (HCS3)	M4K2044	F10c H1c A9a G2a
CI070138 (JCSG7)	M4K2044	F5c
CI070137 (HIN3)	M4K2046	F6a H4d H4c H2c
CI070113 (HIN3)	E6201	F3a E9a E9c E9d B7c
CI070112 (HCS3)	E6201	D6d
CI070110 (JCSG7)	E6201	D12c B9a B9c D12a A2a

Crystals will be left for a few days to see if they grow further before mounting them.

